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The Workforce in OECD Countries

The workforce in OECD countries has grown by an average of 11.06% between 2011 and 2023. The OECD calculates the value of the workforce, and data is available for the period 2011-2023.

The Workforce in OECD Countries in 2023. The analysis of the workforce in OECD countries for 2023 reveals interesting differences and similarities among nations, highlighting the size and economic characteristics of each country. With a total workforce of 167.116 million units, the United States ranks first among OECD countries, reflecting its large population and strong, diversified economy. Japan and Mexico follow with 69.252 million and 60.585 million units, respectively, underscoring the economic importance of these nations within the OECD. Japan's workforce is particularly significant given the country's high population density and advanced technology industry, while Mexico, with a rapidly growing young population, shows an expanding labor market. Germany, with 44.468 million units, represents the largest workforce in Europe, a reflection of its robust industrial economy, while the United Kingdom and Turkey follow with 34.551 million and 34.881 million units, respectively. These countries exhibit diversified economies with strong service and industrial sectors. France, with 30.852 million units, and South Korea, with 29.203 million units, also demonstrate their economic importance within the OECD context. Italy, with a workforce of 25.527 million units, and Spain, with 23.900 million units, are among the countries with the largest workforces in Southern Europe. These countries face significant economic challenges, including high unemployment rates, especially among youth, and the need for structural reforms. Canada, with 21.326 million units, reflects a substantial workforce in a country with a vast geographic area and a diverse population. Colombia and Poland, with 25.365 million and 17.467 million units, respectively, show dynamic and rapidly growing labor markets. Colombia represents one of Latin America's emerging markets, while Poland is a major developing country in Europe, benefiting from foreign investments and favorable economic policies. Nordic countries such as Sweden, with 5.773 million units, Finland, with 2.852 million units, and Norway, with 2.999 million units, exhibit smaller but highly productive workforces, with high living standards and well-developed welfare systems. Denmark, with 3.179 million units, and Iceland, with 228 thousand units, follow this trend of prosperous economies with a strong emphasis on quality of life and social equity. Australia and New Zealand, with 14.610 million and 3.038 million units, respectively, represent significant workforces in the Oceania region, with diversified economies and strong trade links with Asia. Israel, with 4.477 million units, shows a small but dynamic workforce, focused on technology and innovation. Benelux countries, such as Belgium with 5.323 million units and the Netherlands with 10.139 million units, represent strong European economies, benefiting from a strategic geographic position and highly industrialized economies. Luxembourg, with 339 thousand units, although having one of the smallest workforces, boasts one of the highest per capita GDPs in the world, thanks to its financial and banking sector. Eastern and Central European countries, such as the Czech Republic with 5.195 million units, Hungary with 4.941 million units, Slovakia with 2.772 million units, and Slovenia with 1.027 million units, exhibit smaller but growing workforces, with economies rapidly recovering from the post-

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communist transition. Latvia, with 951 thousand units, and Lithuania, with 1.547 million units, follow a similar path of growth and economic development. Greece, with 4.715 million units, continues to struggle with significant economic challenges, including recovery from a long economic crisis and high unemployment rates. Ireland, with 2.773 million units, shows a growing workforce, benefiting from a dynamic economy and significant foreign investments, especially in the technology and pharmaceutical sectors. Finally, smaller countries like Estonia, with 748 thousand units, and Costa Rica, with 2.300 million units, demonstrate limited but growing workforces, with economies benefiting from policies favorable to innovation and sustainable development.

Workforce Trends in OECD Countries Between 2011 and 2023. The analysis of workforce data in OECD countries between 2011 and 2023 reveals significant variations in absolute and percentage terms, highlighting different economic and demographic trends. Starting with the United States, which shows a significant increase in the workforce, rising from 153.617 million units in 2011 to 167.116 million units in 2023, with an absolute change of 13.499 million units, equivalent to 8.79%. This increase reflects sustained economic growth and a continuous ability to create jobs, despite challenges related to automation and the need to update workforce skills. Japan, which already had one of the largest workforces, grew from 65.955 million units to 69.252 million units, with an increase of 3.297 million units (5.00%). This result is notable given the country's demographic difficulties, such as an aging population and low birth rate. Germany's workforce increased by 3.283 million units, rising from 41.185 million to 44.468 million units, with a growth of 7.97%. Germany continues to be Europe's economic powerhouse, supported by a strong manufacturing industry and a robust labor market. Italy saw a more modest increase in the workforce, rising from 24.659 million to 25.527 million units, with an increase of 868 thousand units (3.52%). This reflects persistent economic challenges, including the need for structural reforms to stimulate growth and employment. France recorded an increase in the workforce of 2.604 million units, rising from 28.248 million to 30.852 million units (9.22%). This increase indicates a post-crisis economic recovery, but the French labor market faces challenges such as high youth unemployment. The United Kingdom saw a workforce growth of 2.585 million units, rising from 31.966 million to 34.551 million units (8.09%). This increase reflects relative economic stability and strong labor demand in various sectors, despite uncertainty caused by Brexit. Mexico recorded one of the largest absolute increases, with an increase of 10.863 million units, rising from 49.722 million to 60.585 million units (21.85%). This reflects the country's economic and demographic growth, with a young population entering the labor market. Among the countries with the largest percentage increases are Luxembourg, with a growth of 43.64%, rising from 236 thousand to 339 thousand units. Israel also recorded a strong increase of 39.73%, rising from 3.204 million to 4.477 million units, indicating robust economic and demographic growth. South Korea saw an increase in the workforce of 3.814 million units (15.02%), rising from 25.389 million to 29.203 million units, reflecting sustained economic growth and rapid industrialization. Sweden recorded a growth of 15.07%, with an increase of 756 thousand units, rising from 5.017 million to 5.773 million units. On the other hand, some countries saw a decrease in the workforce. Greece recorded a reduction of 221 thousand units, falling from 4.936 million to 4.715 million units (-4.48%), reflecting persistent economic difficulties and high unemployment rates. Latvia also saw a decrease in the workforce of 77 thousand units (-7.49%), falling from 1.028 million to 951 thousand units. The Czech Republic recorded a slight decrease in the workforce of 28 thousand units (-0.54%), falling from 5.223 million to 5.195 million units, while Portugal saw a reduction of 101 thousand units (-1.86%), falling from 5.426 million to 5.325 million units. Among Nordic countries, Norway saw an increase in the workforce of 379 thousand units (14.47%), rising from 2.620 million to 2.999 million units. Iceland recorded an impressive growth of 27.37%, with an increase of 49 thousand units, rising from 179 thousand to 228 thousand units. In Oceania, Australia saw a significant workforce growth of 2.796 million units (23.67%), rising from 11.814 million to 14.610 million units, while New Zealand recorded an increase of 30.67%, with an increase of 713 thousand units, rising from 2.325 million to 3.038 million units. In Latin America, Chile saw an increase in the workforce

of 1.628 million units (19.60%), rising from 8.306 million to 9.934 million units, while Colombia recorded an increase of 3.630 million units (16.70%), rising from 21.735 million to 25.365 million units. In Central and Eastern Europe, Hungary saw an increase in the workforce of 716 thousand units (16.95%), rising from 4.225 million to 4.941 million units. Poland recorded a slight increase of 246 thousand units (1.43%), rising from 17.221 million to 17.467 million units.

Economic Policies for Workforce Growth in OECD Countries. Economic policies aimed at workforce development in OECD countries must be multidimensional, addressing various challenges and opportunities to create a favorable environment for sustainable and inclusive economic growth. First, it is essential to invest in education and continuous training to ensure that the workforce is adequately prepared for the needs of the 21st-century labor market. This includes improving access to and quality of primary and higher education, promoting vocational training and apprenticeship programs aligned with market demands, and encouraging lifelong learning to ensure that workers can adapt to technological and market changes. Digital skills become particularly important in a context where automation and artificial intelligence are transforming many industries. Policies aimed at bridging the digital divide and providing advanced technological skills can help workers remain competitive and seize new opportunities. At the same time, it is crucial to support innovation and technology. This can be achieved through increased investments in research and development (R&D), creating a favorable ecosystem for innovation that includes tax incentives for companies investing in R&D and public-private partnerships that promote collaboration between universities, research centers, and industry. Moreover, policies must favor the adoption of new technologies in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which often lack the resources necessary to invest in innovation independently. Innovation policies not only stimulate economic growth but also create new jobs in emerging sectors, thus contributing to workforce development. Labor market flexibility is another crucial element. Policies that promote flexible work contracts and facilitate labor mobility can help reduce unemployment and improve workforce adaptability. However, it is important to balance flexibility with job security, ensuring that workers are not exposed to excessive precariousness. To this end, social security schemes can be introduced that offer a safety net for workers, including adequate unemployment benefits and retraining programs for those who lose their jobs. In addition, policies that support work-life balance, such as paid parental leave and flexible working hours, can improve worker well-being and increase labor market participation, particularly among women. Promoting inclusivity in the labor market is fundamental for sustainable development. Active employment policies that aim to integrate disadvantaged groups, such as young people, women, the elderly, and migrants, can contribute to greater equity and social cohesion. Mentoring programs, incentives for hiring protected categories, and initiatives for the inclusion of ethnic and racial minorities are examples of measures that can improve participation and inclusion in the labor market. Additionally, promoting entrepreneurship and self-employment through access to financing, training, and administrative support can create additional job opportunities and stimulate innovation. The demographic dimension represents a growing challenge for many OECD countries, with rapidly aging populations. Policies to prolong active working life, such as promoting active aging and pension system reform, are essential. Encouraging companies to retain and hire older workers, through tax breaks and skill updating programs, can help maintain an experienced and productive workforce. At the same time, policies that support birth rates and work-life balance are crucial to counteracting demographic decline. The internationalization of the labor market and worker mobility among OECD countries can significantly contribute to workforce development. Facilitating labor mobility through the mutual recognition of professional qualifications, reducing bureaucratic barriers, and promoting work exchange programs can enrich human capital and stimulate innovation. In this context, policies that promote international collaboration in education and training, such as Erasmus programs and similar, can prepare young people to compete in a global labor market. Economic policies for workforce development must also address the challenges posed by climate change and promote a just transition to a green economy. The adoption of sustainable technologies and practices can create new

jobs in the renewable energy, energy efficiency, and waste management sectors. Training and reskilling policies specific to green sectors can ensure that workers are prepared for the opportunities offered by the ecological transition. Moreover, incentives for companies adopting sustainable practices and policies promoting the circular economy can contribute to sustainable economic growth. Finally, the importance of governance and institutions cannot be underestimated. Governments must ensure that policies are well-designed, implemented, and monitored. Transparency, accountability, and stakeholder participation are fundamental for the success of economic policies. Public-private partnerships, collaboration with international organizations, and the involvement of civil society can strengthen the effectiveness of workforce development policies.

Conclusions. Between 2011 and 2023, the average value of the workforce in the considered OECD countries grew by 11.06%. The countries with the highest workforce growth are Luxembourg with +43.64%, Israel with +39.73%, and Turkey with +32.01%. However, some countries experienced a reduction in workforce value between 2011 and 2023, namely the Czech Republic with -0.54%, Portugal with -1.86%, Greece with -4.48%, and Latvia with -7.49%. The total workforce in the OECD countries is approximately 689 million people. However, about 50% of this workforce is allocated in 4 countries, namely the USA, Japan, Mexico, and Germany. However, the workforce of OECD countries is smaller compared to China's workforce. According to Statista, China's workforce in 2023 was 740 million people. India's workforce is estimated at around 600 million units. Therefore, OECD countries tend to be smaller compared to Asian giants in terms of workforce size.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

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Appendix

Forza lavoro nei paesi OCSE (2011 vs 2023)

